

THE IMPACT OF THE HEALTH CRISIS ON SPORTS ORGANIZATIONS

Auteur 1 : FILALI ALLACH Mariam,

Auteur 2 : BENNANI Hayat,

Auteur 3 : BELKADI Issam,

FILALI ALLACH Mariam¹, Full Time Professor

ESLSCA Business School – Campus Rabat

fi.meryem@gmail.com

BENNANI Hayat², Full Time Professor

ESLSCA Business School – Campus Rabat

hy.bennani@gmail.com

BELKADI Issam³, Full Time Professor

ESLSCA Business School – Campus Rabat

issam.belkadi@gmail.com

Déclaration de divulgation : L'auteur n'a pas connaissance de quelconque financement qui pourrait affecter l'objectivité de cette étude.

Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : FILALI ALLACH. M, BENNANI. H & BELKADI. I (2022) « The impact of the health crisis on sports organizations » , Revue African Scientific Journal, Volume 3, Numéro 11, pp : 148-162.

Date de soumission : Janvier 2022

Date de publication : Avril 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6513085

Copyright © 2022 – ASJ

Abstract

The effects of COVID-19 continue to be felt in the health field, educational, financial and business institutions around the world, and the sports ecosystem is no different. Containment has caused sports sessions to be canceled. Clubs and venues have had to close their doors. Owners, broadcasters and sponsors are trying to manage the impacts and implications of event cancellations and modifications.

The situation has raised many questions. How do you simultaneously manage the costs, minimize the losses, and plan for a future that, in the short and long term, may no longer look like the past? Can new technology help businesses be more resilient? Have grants and facilities helped businesses cope with the crisis? As the pandemic looks set to last for some time, will the entire sports ecosystem have to find new ways to deal with threats to financial and business continuity due to disrupted cash flow, redundancy and recruitment issues?

Keywords : Health Crisis – Organization – Resilience - Sport Management

Introduction

The health crisis the world is experiencing today is undoubtedly without precedent. In order to combat the spread of COVID-19, Morocco has put in place a number of exceptional measures: border closures, stopping international flights, restrictions on inland transport, curfews, lockdowns and cancellations of gatherings, etc.

These measures, as in many countries, have limited or even put a halt to the activities of several major sectors such as transport, tourism, catering...and the sport that has been particularly affected by this pandemic, which has led to the postponements, or cancellation of the end-suite. Sports events, the closure of sports halls, and the decline in activity among specialty brands, etc. Faced with this situation, many companies in the sector have been forced to reduce their staff, to go into debt in order to survive or even to go bankrupt. On the other hand, a handful of them were able to mitigate the effects of the crisis by rethinking their economic models offering innovative products and services, which will enable them to be more effective in the future.

Given the magnitude of the effects of COVID-19 on the Moroccan sport landscape as a whole, and given the important role that sport normally plays in both health and economic terms, It was essential to conduct an in-depth study to measure the impact of this crisis on this sector. The aim of the study is also to identify measures that the government could put in place to support and relaunch an industry that accounts for 1.1% of GDP and employs no less than 240,000 jobs.

Pandemics lead to huge negative economic, social and security effects. In this article, we will try to shed light on some of the impacts of Covid 19 pandemic on sports organizations worldwide.

Our work focuses on a study and analysis of the impact of different aspects related to the Covid-19 crisis on sports facilities. The method used, called the quantitative method, aims to deduce measurable conclusions.

1. Management of the health crisis :

Before talking about the effects of the covid 19 pandemic on sports organizations we will talk about where it started, how it spread all over the world and how it was managed by different governments.

1.1. The Covid 19 crisis

COVID-19 is highly contagious pathogenic viral infection initiated from Wuhan seafood wholesale market of China on December 2019 and spread rapidly around the whole world due to onward transmission (Rajan K M., & al. 2020). This recent outbreak of novel coronavirus (COV) is causing respiratory infections such as common cold, dry cough, fever, headache, dyspnea, pneumonia, and finally Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) in humans (Mohapatra et al., 2020). The coronavirus has the same mode of transmission as two other viruses: the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in 2002 and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) in 2012 (World Health Organization, 2020). All these viruses are a zoonotic form as they transmitted from animals to humans. COVID-19 thought to have originated in the wet market that sold live animals in Wuhan, China (Pantano et al., 2020).

Initially COVID-19 was centered on China but then spread to other parts of Asia. Other countries including Italy and Iran then sustained a high level of cases. The majority of Europe affected with the United States following. Other countries including the United Kingdom and Brazil have been heavily affected (Sharma et al., 2020).

1.2. Crisis management

Management of the Covid-19 was not an easy endeavor.

To face this worldwide pandemic, governments across the world scrambled with emergency actions, such as lockdowns; travel restrictions; testing and quarantining; and economic packages. This bundle of highly restrictive, sometimes intrusive, non-pharmaceutical interventions may cause substantial economic and social costs, while affecting individual behavior, mental health and social security (Haug et al. 2020).

2. The impact of the health crisis on sports organizations

2.1. The impact of the health crisis on societies and economies of the world

The covid 19 pandemic brought about terror about an economic and social crisis.

The COVID-19 pandemic has sparked fears of an economic crisis and recession caused by a high level of uncertainty (Nicola et al., 2020). All aspects of society have been affected by COVID-19 with new social behaviors such as social distancing and self-isolation have been implemented. This is in distinct contrast to the internationalization policy of the past that promoted global travel within the sport industry.

According to Ivanov (2020) characterizes the risks of epidemic in three elements: first, its unpredictability, second, the disruption it generates, the ripple effect of the disruption, and finally, the long-term duration of its effects. Often management problems and unpreparedness on the part of leaders are at the root of crises that threaten the management and survival of the organization.

The COVID-19 pandemic is not only hugely disrupting the global economy but also virtually bringing the sports sector to its knees. The impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) has been dramatic in the sports world. For the majority of participation starved recreational players, venues and facilities, sponsors and broadcasters, and sporting organizations and leagues, the impact has been swift and severe. It is important to know that the sports industry estimated value was 471 US Billion dollars in 2018 (Statista 2020).

2.2. The impact of the health crisis on sports organizations

The effects of the covid 19 pandemic on sports organization were remarkable.

Due to the restrictions of social distancing and attempts to control the spread of the virus many events, from local grassroots events to international competition, have been canceled or postponed such as the F1 Grand Prix, World Athletics Championships, Wimbledon, UEFA Euro 2020, and Tour de France has been rescheduled or canceled. The most important was the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, which been postponed to summer 2021 (Yamamura et al. 2020). The major players in the sport supply chain (e.g. teams, sponsors, hotels, airlines and transport operators) have suffered unfathomable damages. On sporting content been severely challenge by the pandemic, especially given their significant long-term and largely fixed rights deals with major leagues, having turned to sport as a major platform for investment over the last decade or so (Hutchins et al., 2019). Sponsors have also suffered, especially those relying on a combination of event exposure, player endorsements and retail sales (Dašić et al. 2020). The warning of corona disease affected the health fitness manufacturing such as fitness center, yoga, and aerobic center, causing job loss more thousands of many coaches and administrative workers (Shereen et al. 2020).

The sudden and unexpected outbreak of coronavirus in the world has caused profound changes in the process of managing sports and leisure, and the economic, social, and cultural situation of the sports industry, and it seems that the effect of these changes will last long after the disease is controlled (Keshkar et al. 2021).

The current pandemic has had a massive negative impact on the economics of professional team sports. One of the solutions would be the creation of a consolidation fund, financed by the future broadcasting deals, to support clubs with a deficit on transfer fees and players suffering a pay cut that would allowed redeem their claims within five years (Szymanski 2020)

Among one of the main sources of revenue of professional team sports, gate receipts have certainly suffered the most immediately negative effect. The social distancing measures leading to events canceled or staged behind closed doors have deprived the event organizers of an instant cash flow. Cancellation of events may lead to a renegotiation of broadcasting deals that represent the main source of revenue for professional team sports. (Keshkar et al. 2021). The media and broadcasters relying.

There are two major outcomes of the crisis. The first based on extrapolating the behavior of firms based on previous crises in that the sport industry will gradually return to normal, the other is that the industry radically changes based on societal needs (Ratten 2020). In their analysis of the post-pandemic implications for sport, Grix et al. 2020 foreshadowed three legacy issues. First, they argued that the pandemic should force governments to re-evaluate their investment decisions in sport, most notably the tension between elite and participation resourcing, the latter a perennial loser to the former's allure. Secondly, that the crisis will significantly increase the use of remote and online work and business, including those in the sport sector. Finally, Grix and colleagues suggested that the remarkable growth of esports during the pandemic, as well as its use by mainstream sports like Formula 1 and FIFA to enhance its traditional product with new layers, would continue. Both volumes of the special issue pick-up on aspects of these predictions, in addition to many others (Grix et al. 2020).

3. Results and discussion

The sample of the study includes 50 private companies representing the sport industry in Morocco (fitness centers, third-party equipment, agencies, clubs, specialist retailers, media, start-ups, etc.). Spread over the entire national territory, they account for a total of eight hundred and twenty million dirhams.

Our study done in two stages. First, we developed a quantitative approach to collecting data through a questionnaire administered by email and telephone. We thus used the «Likert» scale to first measure the importance of the impact of the health crisis, in a general way, on these organizations before analyzing more specifically the financial impact, by assessing how the turnover, cash and payroll studied affected. In addition, we identified the various ways in which these organizations have been able to cope with this crisis and their assessments of the measures taken by the government.

In a second phase, we organized focus groups and one-to-one meetings to identify concrete recommendations from the main stakeholders to mitigate the effects of the health crisis and to relaunch and develop the sport industry in Morocco.

3.1. Results

Table 1. What type of structures do you represent?

Source : authors

78% of the organizations that participated in the survey are private companies, 20% are clubs and 2% are self-employed.

Table 2. How do you assess the impact of the COVID-19 crisis on your structure?

Source : authors

In terms of the impact of the Covid 19 crisis on the structure, 71% of the structures noticed a very important impact of the Covid 19 crisis on their structure, 27% an important impact, 2% a little important impact.

Table 3. Has the COVID-19 crisis impacted your sales for the year 2020?

Source : authors

Regarding the impact of the Covid 19 crisis on revenue 94% responded that their revenue was impact during 2020, compared to 6% who responded no.

Table 4. Has this drop in sales jeopardized your structure?

Source : authors

71% of respondents confirmed that the decline in sales has jeopardized their structure, while 29% answered no.

Table 5. Has the Covid-19 crisis affected the cash flow of your structure?

Source : authors

In terms of cash flow, almost all (92%) said that the Covid 19 crisis had an impact on their organization's cash flow.

Table 6. Has COVID-19 forced you to review the human resources organization of your structure?

Source : authors

As for the organization of human resources, 71% declared that they were obliged to review the organization of human resources in their structure because of the Covid 19 crisis, while 29% kept the same organization.

Table 7. Have you had to let go of any of your employees?

Source : authors

Following the Covid crisis, 53% of the structures were not obliged to separate from some of their employees against 47% were obliged to separate from some of their employees.

Table 8. Despite the crisis, were you able to recruit new employees?

Source : authors

During the Covid 19 crisis, 76% of organizations were unfortunately unable to recruit new employees. However, only 24% were able to recruit.

Table 9. Has your compensation policy been affected?

Source : authors

76 % of organizations stated that their compensation policy has been impacted versus 24% that it has not.

Table 10. Have you benefited from the measures taken by the government for companies in your sector to cope with the crisis?

Source : authors

75% said they never benefited from the measures taken by the government for companies in their sector to cope with the crisis.

Table 11. Do you think that these measures were equal to the crisis?

Source : authors

84% of facilities believe that the measures taken were not up to par.

3.2. Discussion

The large majority of the sports structures have noticed a very important impact of the Covid 19 crisis on their structure.

The Covid-19 crisis has not spared sports companies, whose average revenue decline is estimated to be about 70% in 2020 compared to 2019.

94 % of them declare, in 2020, a decrease in their budget.

The main difficulty encountered by companies as a result of the health crisis is the cash flow problem. Concerns about debt and equity remain in the background, showing that companies are still driven by the need to survive.

The Covid-19 has accelerated the process of digitalization of sports players, as these tools have proven necessary to ensure the continuity of activity for most of them. Some sports companies were digitalized and many sports associations, which were not very committed to digitalization before the crisis, have developed a plan B, have offered remote coaching or an online course platform since the crisis, and have thus been able to resist the crisis. The implementation of digital tools and their increased use have thus been one of the conditions of survival to the crisis for most of the sport actors.

Indeed, the Covid 19 crisis has affected the turnover of the company and its treasury.

As far as the organization of human resources is concerned, the majority of the structures were obliged to review the organization of human resources in their structure because of the Covid 19 crisis: some structures were unfortunately unable to recruit new employees and were even obliged to separate from some of their employees.

Regarding the measures taken by the government for companies, a large part of the structures interviewed declared that they had never benefited from them and think that the measures taken were not up to the mark.

Conclusion

Create a label for companies that encourage their employees to play sports.

Launch a national sport infrastructure upgrade program through public-private partnerships.

Relaunch school and university sport within the framework of a public private partnership in order to broaden the base of practitioners but also support companies in the sector (infrastructure, animation...).

Adapt existing training courses in sport management to meet the exact needs of the market.

Rehabilitate youth centres with the objective of creating a concept of life that promotes the practice of sport on a daily basis.

Encourage sports federations to delegate the organization of their events with budgets exceeding 250,000 dirhams to specialized agencies.

Establish a label for sports federations and associations that meet a number of requirements in terms of management, human resources and good governance.

Implement a grant program to encourage the digitalization of sports federations and associations.

Bibliography

Dašić, D. R., Tošić, M. Z., & Deletić, V. (2020). “The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the advertising and sponsorship industry in sport”. *Bizinfo (Blace)*, 11(2), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.5937/bizinfo2002105D>

Dmitry Ivanov, Ajay Das 2020 Coronavirus (COVID-19/SARS-CoV-2) and supply chain resilience : a research note. *International journal of integrated supply management : IJISM*. - Genève : Inderscience Enterprises, ISSN 1741-8097, ZDB-ID 2193775-8. - Vol. 13.2020, 1, p. 90-102

Grix, J., et al., 2020. “The impact of Covid-19 on sport. *International journal of sport policy and politics*”. Epub ahead of print 27 November 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19406940.2020.1851285>

Harleen K, Singh T, Arya YK, Mittal S. “Physical Fitness and Exercise During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Qualitative Enquiry Front”. *Psychol.*, 29 October 2020. doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.590172

Haug, N., Geyrhofer, L., Londei, A. et al. Ranking the effectiveness of worldwide COVID-19 government interventions. *Nat Hum Behav* 4, 1303–1312 (2020). [doi: 10.1038/s41562-020-01009-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-01009-0).

Hutchins, B., Li, B., & Rowe, D. (2019). “Over-the-top sport: Live streaming services, changing coverage rights markets and the growth of media sport portals”. *Media, Culture & Society*, 41(7), 975–994. [doi: 10.1177/0163443719857623](https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443719857623)

Keshkar S, Lawrence I, Dodds M, Morris E, Mahoney T, Heisey K, et al. The Role of Culture in Sports Sponsorship: An Update. *Ann Appl Sport Sci*. 2019; 7(1): 57-81. [doi:10.29252/aassjournal.7.1.57](https://doi.org/10.29252/aassjournal.7.1.57)

Mohapatra RK, Pintilie L, Kandi V, Sarangi AK, Das D, Sahu R, Perekhoda L. “The recent challenges of highly contagious COVID-19, causing respiratory infections: Symptoms, diagnosis, transmission, possible vaccines, animal models, and immunotherapy”. *Chem Biol*

Nicola, M., Alsafi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C., Agha, M. and Agha,

R. (2020), “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): a review”, *International Journal of Surgery*, Vol. 78 No. 1, pp. 185-193.

Pantano, E., Pizzi, G., Scarpi, D. and Dennis, C. (2020), “Competing during a pandemic? Retailers’ ups and downs during the COVID-19 outbreak”, *Journal of Business Research*, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.036.

Rajan, K, M., & al., (2020) “The recent challenges of highly contagious COVID-19, causing respiratory infections: Symptoms, diagnosis, transmission, possible vaccines, animal models, and immunotherapy”, 2020 Nov; 96(5):1187-1208. Doi : 10.1111/cbdd.13761. Epub 2020 Jul 26.

Ratten, V. (2020). “Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) and sport entrepreneurship”. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(6), 1379–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-06-2020-0387>

Sharma, P., Leung, T.Y., Kingshott, R.P., Davcik, N.S. and Cardinali, S. (2020), “Managing uncertainty during a global pandemic: an international business perspective”, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 116 No. 1, pp. 188-192.

Statista. Sports & Fitness <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1087391/global-sports-market-size/Statista 2020>.

Szymanski, S. “Covid-19 and football club insolvency”, paper presented at Reading Online Sport Economics Seminars (ROSES), 2020 April 17th, 2020, available on line at <https://www.soccernomics-agency.com/?p=1670>

Terri, B., Khevyn-Lynn, G., Mathieu, W., Christos, A., Remi, R., & Simone, D., (2021) “COVID-19 impacts on sport governance and management: a global, critical realist perspective” <https://doi.org/10.1080/23750472.2020.1867002>, pp. 99 - 107